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Influence of Iron catalyst in the Carbon Spheres Synthesis for Energy and Electrochemical Applications --Manuscript Draft--

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<p>Please submit a plain text version of your cover letter here.</p> <p>If you are submitting a revision of your manuscript, please do not overwrite your original cover letter. There is an opportunity for you to provide your responses to the reviewers later; please do not add them here.</p>	<p>Dear Editor, we would hereby like to submit the following manuscript (MS) for publication in Small as full paper.</p> <p>The title of the MS is: "Influence of Iron catalyst in the Carbon Spheres Synthesis for Energy and Electrochemical Applications" The authors are: Manuela Scarselli, Francesca Limosani, Maurizio Passacantando, Franco D'Orazio, Michele Nardone, Ilaria Cacciotti, Fabiana Arduini, Eric Gautron, Maurizio De Crescenzi</p> <p>This work illustrates a comprehensive investigation on the chemical vapour deposition synthesis process applied to obtain carbon nano-spheres (CSs). Although these carbon structures have recently attracted great attention for their high chemical stability, low density, high surface-to-volume ratio, and satisfactory conductivity, there are few papers that try to link their potential applications to the structural properties. In this paper, we first show that slight changes applied during the synthesis process produce CSs that differ in the inner graphitic assembly. In addition, the use of iron catalyst during the reaction process confers the carbon spheres a ferromagnetic response at room temperature.</p> <p>In the second part of the paper, we investigate on the link between the CS structural properties found and their potential use as active material in three innovative applications. In particular, we focus on the following macroscopic properties: 1) the super-hydrophobicity, for which the presence of iron is not essential, while iron marked the difference in the measured 2) photoresponse as well as in the 3) electrochemical behavior. The results are promising and evidence that the iron contained inside the carbon spheres might be exploited for some targeted applications.</p> <p>We think that the subject of the manuscript adheres to the scope of this journal that deals with the different aspects of nanomaterial fabrication and characterization with distinct attention to their potential technological applications.</p> <p>On behalf of the authors Sincerely yours, Manuela Scarselli</p>
Do you or any of your co-authors have a conflict of interest to declare?	No. The authors declare no conflict of interest.
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Abstract:	<p>Carbon spheres of nanometric dimension are known since the first studies on the synthesis of fullerenes. Their shape originates from the curvature of a carbon sheet similar to fullerenes, but with numerous graphitic rings that regulate the inside structure and the formation of open edges at the surface. This paper focuses on the structural and electronic characterization of carbon spheres obtained from a targeted chemical vapor deposition synthesis process. Two different set of samples are analyzed in detail, in particular, the electron microscopies and Raman spectroscopy help understanding the morphology and the graphitic-sp² arrangement of the carbon atoms in the architectures. In addition, the iron catalyst used during the reaction process confers the carbon spheres a ferromagnetic response at room temperature. Therefore, both the structural properties of the samples and the active contribution of iron mark the difference in the measured photoresponse as well as in the electrochemical behavior. The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy study addresses these points by giving information on the composition and the iron chemical state in the assembly. The collected results underline the advantages offered by this synthesis route and the properties of the carbon spheres as active nanomaterial for sustainable applications.</p>

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6 **Electrochemical Applications**
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11 *Manuela Scarselli**, *Francesca Limosani*, *Maurizio Passacantando*, *Franco D'Orazio*, *Michele*
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17 List of changes to the revised manuscript:
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21 **In the 2. Results and Discussion**
22

23 Paragraph 2.2 Hydrophobicity: Action taken \Rightarrow entirely deleted together with cited references
24

25 Figure 6: Action taken \Rightarrow deleted
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27 Figure 7: Action taken \Rightarrow renumbered as Fig. 6
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29 Figure 8: Action taken \Rightarrow renumbered as Fig. 7
30

31 End of Page 16: Action taken \Rightarrow Changed the sentence: “*While these differences do not*
32 *influence the super hydrophobic behavior found in the CS assemblies, we think that are*
33 *responsible of the different light response.*” into \Rightarrow “*These structural differences strongly*
34 *influence the observed light response.*”
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40 **In the 3. Conclusion**
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42 Action taken \Rightarrow deleted the following text: “*The observed differences in the outer surface*
43 *morphology influence in a similar way the hydrophobic behavior, being both of them super*
44 *hydrophobic. On the contrary, both the*”
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50 **In the 4. Experimental: 4.2 Sample Characterization**
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52 Action taken \Rightarrow deleted the following text: “*Static advanced contact angles (CA) were*
53 *measured by increasing the volume of the deionized water drop by steps of 1 μ L, until a final*
54 *volume is reached. The contact angle was imaged 15 s after drop casting to ensure that the*
55 *droplet reached its equilibrium position. The images obtained with a CCD camera where*
56 *analyzed with a plugin [19] from the open-source software (ImageJ) to estimate the contact*
57 *angle values. Every contact angle value reported is the average over five measurements. In the*
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images reported in the paper, the drop contour was interpolated with a cubic B-Spline curve to reach subpixel resolution.”

Action taken \Rightarrow deleted reference [19]

References

Action taken \Rightarrow list renumbered after deleting the references numbers from [26] to [35].

Checked the reference format

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Influence of Iron catalyst in the Carbon Spheres Synthesis for Energy and Electrochemical Applications

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Keywords: chemical vapor deposition, magnetic properties, structural properties, photon-energy conversion, electrochemical response

Abstract

1
2 Carbon spheres of nanometric dimension are known since the first studies on the synthesis of
3
4 fullerenes. Their shape originates from the curvature of a carbon sheet similar to fullerenes, but
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6 with numerous graphitic rings that regulate the inside structure and the formation of open edges
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8 at the surface. This paper focuses on the structural and electronic characterization of carbon
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10 spheres obtained from a chemical vapor deposition synthesis process. Two different set of
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12 samples are analyzed in detail, in particular, electron microscopies and Raman spectroscopy
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18 carbon spheres a ferromagnetic response at room temperature. Therefore, both the structural
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20 properties of the samples and the active contribution of iron mark the difference in the measured
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22 photoresponse as well as in the electrochemical behavior. The X-ray photoelectron
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24 spectroscopy study addresses these points by giving information on the composition and the
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26 iron chemical state in the assembly. The collected results underline the advantages offered by
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28 this nanomaterial for sustainable applications.
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1. Introduction

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46 The discovery of fullerenes ^[1] marked the beginning of a new era for carbon allotropes of
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48 nanometer dimension, as they are the first cage-like structure with a surface curvature that
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50 originates from the insertion of pentagonal carbon rings into the hexagonal graphene layer.
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52 Since then, the scientific community started the investigation on other curved carbon
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54 nanostructures that could enrich the current knowledge of the structural and electronic
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56 properties of quantum size-related materials. Added to this, there is a strong interest in
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58 producing small-scale materials for technological applications. ^[2] Before fullerenes, the most
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1 studied and well-characterized spherical carbon materials were carbon blacks, ^[3,4] and their
2 properties found several industrial applications. ^[5] Different from fullerenes, the carbon spheres
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4 have an internal structure constituted of numerous graphitic sheets that form mostly closed
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6 shells but also waving flakes whose open edges yield reaction sites located in the outer surface.
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8 Spherically shaped carbon materials, not including the fullerene family, have been given many
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10 names; these include carbon balls, carbon nanospheres, carbon microbeads, carbon blacks,
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12 onions, and others. It is clear that properties like size, morphology and inner structure can vary
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14 substantially, nevertheless the generic term carbon spheres (CSs) applies to all carbon materials
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16 that have a spherical or near spherical shape. ^[6-8] The CS structures can be classified according
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18 to the size, degree of graphitization and the resulting orientation of the carbon layers in the
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20 texture: concentric, radial or random. ^[8] Therefore, they can be distinguished in: 1) carbon
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22 onions, with well-organized inner structure and diameter ranging between 2÷20 nm; 2) carbon
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24 spheres, less graphitized structures with diameters between 50÷1000 nm, and 3) carbon beads,
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26 that can have diameters up to tents of microns with a poor graphitization degree. Generally,
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28 each CS morphology derives from the synthesis route used. ^[6,7] In the last decades, some
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30 synthesis processes adopted for the production of carbon nanotubes, led by chance many side
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32 products including CSs. ^[9] Therefore, some of these routes have been adapted to obtain CS as
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34 the main product but it is difficult to identify the best method since some of the parameters that
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36 regulate the growth of other carbon nanostructures ^[6,7] seem to be less specific for the CSs. The
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38 key target is to ensure that the CSs are monodispersed and the outer surface properties are
39
40 controlled. Several published reviews give an exhaustive description of the most significant CS
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42 synthesis routes ^[6,7] including arc-discharge ^[10], laser ablation ^[11], chemical vapor deposition
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44 ^[12], and thermal pyrolysis ^[13]. In detail, the arc-discharge and laser ablation methods require
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46 high energies and temperature for the synthesis and produce CSs of variable dimension. In
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48 addition, the yields tend to be low and the final materials require additional purification routes
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50 before their use. In the framework of alternative and new synthesis processes the chemical

vapor deposition (CVD) turns out to be the most flexible and relatively low cost technique for an efficient and controlled production of carbon species.^[6,7,12] In the process, a volatile carbon source decomposes and the carbon atoms rearrange to give well-organized carbon crystalline nanostructures. This method is versatile because it is able to produce CSs with well-defined characteristics changing some of the growth parameters such as the carbon source, the temperature and the gas pressure. It is also possible to add a metal catalyst in the reaction for lessening the growth conditions, favor the dissociation of the carbon precursor and the formation of the graphene sheets that will constitute the CSs.^[14] The CSs are synthesized using a catalytic carbonization of methane over rare earth metal oxides or iron at a temperature higher than 1000°C,^[15] or using high pressure processes (30 MPa), like the carbonization of polyethylene–poly-(vinyl chloride),^[16] and in carbon vapor from the decomposition of b-SiC powder.^[17] Ferrocene as catalyst and different carbon precursors have been used in CVD operating at temperatures ranging from 900-1000 °C.^[18] CSs of variable size were obtained at relatively low temperature (650 °C) from the decomposition of acetylene over transition metal salts supported on kaolin substrate, the CSs obtained have variable size range with some side products like carbon nanotubes.^[19] Other processes, like hydrothermal, reduction and template routes, gave good results, as described in detail in the literature.^[6,7] This paper first illustrates the a CVD often referred as floating catalyst process, in which both the iron catalyst and a carbon precursor are dispersed in a solution. Subsequently, drops of solution are injected into the hot zone of a furnace with the help of a gas carrier (argon) and an additional carbon gas precursor (acetylene). When the main elements (catalyst and carbon precursors) reach the high temperature zone, decompose in the elemental form and the production of carbon species starts. The main advantages offered by this process are: 1) the synthesis does not require any substrate; 2) the final yield is proportional to the reaction time; 3) there are few side products coming from the reaction; 4) the CSs have a narrow size distribution; 5) the reaction temperature is relatively low (750°C- 800°C) compared to other synthesis routes^[6,7] and 6) the production has

1 a relatively low price. Mostly importantly, the encapsulation of catalyst particles in the spheres
2 can be exploited in some applications, as illustrated in this paper. In particular, this paper
3 focuses on the synthesis of two different sets of CSs obtained from the floating catalyst CVD
4 process. These were subjected to different characterization techniques including scanning
5 electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy and X-ray
6 photoelectron spectroscopy in order to qualify their structure, morphology and chemical
7 composition. The use of iron as catalyst during the synthesis confers to the CSs magnetic
8 properties as demonstrated by magnetic characterization. Finally, magnetic and non-magnetic
9 CSs are challenged for energy and electrochemical applications demonstrating the improved
10 performances of magnetic CSs and thus the advantage of using Fe as catalyst.
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26 **2. Results and Discussion**

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31 The experimental results illustrated in this paragraph were collected from two different carbon
32 sphere samples. The first, namely sample A, was obtained from a synthesis process maintaining
33 the argon/acetylene gas flux of 50 sccm/25 sccm, while for the second sample, named B, the
34 argon/acetylene gas flux was kept at 250 sccm/40 sccm (see the experimental paragraph 3.1).
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41 The reaction time, the solution concentration, the injection rate in the hot zone and the growth
42 time were the same for the two processes.
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48 *2.1 Characterization of carbon spheres*

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53 The morphology of the CS samples was first investigated through systematic SEM
54 measurements, **Figure 1**. In particular, Figure 1 (a) reports a low and high magnification (inset)
55 images of sample A. The low magnification evidences the sample homogeneity and the absence
56 of carbonaceous side products, while the inset shows well-defined carbon spheres of variable
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1 diameter. Similarly, Figure 1(b) reports a combination of low and magnification images
2 collected from sample B. No side products or other carbon species appear in the extended image,
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4 and the inset exhibits that these spheres have homogeneous average size but sometimes are
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6 partially welded.
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Figure 1. SEM micrographs of CS samples. (a) Sample A, on large scale no side products or other carbon species are present, scale bar is 5 μm . The image in the inset shows well-defined CSs of different diameter, scale bar is 200 nm. (b) Sample B has similar behavior of the sample A on a large scale image, scale bar is 5 μm , while in the better resolved image in the inset the CSs have homogenous dimensions but some of them are partially welded, scale bar is 200 nm.

The TEM helped investigating the inner and the outer surface structure of both samples. **Figure 2** shows a collection of images of few carbon spheres dispersed on the TEM grid from samples A and B. In particular, Figure 2(a-c) provides some insight into the structure of the spheres from sample A. The inner part is constituted of disordered graphitic sheets while the outer surface is not regular in shape evidencing many protruding graphitic planes that make the surface very defective, Figure 2b. The statistical analysis of the diameter distribution reported in Figure 2(c) gives an average CS diameter of 200 ± 10 nm.

Similarly, Figure 2(d-f) reports the TEM images obtained from sample B. The CSs are composed of graphene layers that, differently from sample A, are more uniformly distributed inside the spheres (Figure 2e) at a relative average distance that ranges between $0.33 \div 0.35$ nm, compatible with that of crystal layers in graphite. The outer surface is more regular and smooth compared to sample A. The average diameter found for this sample from the statistical analysis is 175 ± 10 nm, Figure 2(f).

Figure 2. TEM images of samples A and B. Sample A: (a) Large scale image shows CSs and residual side products; (b) Disordered graphitic planes are present inside and outside the sphere forming open edges (inset); (c) Size distribution histogram. Sample B: (d) Large scale image shows the presence of CSs that form a necklace structure; (e) The graphitic planes are ordered inside the sphere and the outer surface is not smooth (inset); (f) Size distribution diagram. Red arrows in (a) and (d) point to clusters inside the spheres of different electronic contrast.

1 From SEM and TEM studies, we conclude that each synthesis process influenced the inner
2 organization of the graphite sheets that compose the CSs and, mostly important, the outer
3 surface structure, while the average diameter is comparable. The similarity in the sphere size
4 found derives from the identical reaction time of process. The carbon sp^2 hybridization in the
5 sphere assembly come both the electron energy loss (EELS) and Raman spectra (Figure S1 and
6 S2 in the Supplementary Information). The EELS spectra shows two typical sp^2 features similar
7 to that of graphite plasmon losses, but located at lower energy position because of the reduced
8 dimension of the material (Figure S1 in the Supplementary Information). The two main Raman
9 features the D (around 1350 cm^{-1}) and G bands (around 1580 cm^{-1}) that originate from the
10 carbon defects and sp^2 vibrational modes respectively, highlight a high number of structural
11 imperfections and evidence a not perfect degree of graphitization for both samples A and B
12 (Figure S2 in the supplementary Information). These results are comparable to those reported
13 for similar CSs. ^[10,17-19]

14 Interestingly, from the TEM images smaller points of different electronic contrast appear inside
15 the CSs. The arrows in Figures 2(a) and 2(d) highlight some of them. These probably consist
16 of iron catalyst residual particles encapsulated during the reaction process. In order to deepen
17 this point, we followed different routes. Firstly, the presence of catalyst residues in the reaction
18 products can be easily appreciated at the macroscopic level. In fact, when a permanent magnet
19 is approached to a vial containing the CS powder some of it is lifted under the action of the
20 magnet, clearly demonstrating that a portion of the reaction products has a significant magnetic
21 moment, whereas the rest of the material is much more weakly magnetic, **Figure 3**. The
22 observed behavior can only originate from the iron participating to the reaction, since it is the
23 only magnetic element exploited in the synthesis.

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17 **Figure 3.** Image of the magnetic separation of one of the synthesis products. Each sample
18 powder under the action of the permanent magnet shares into two parts, magnetic and non-
19 magnetic one respectively.
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26 Therefore, each sample powder was separated into two parts: one magnetic, that corresponds
27 to the material that responds to the external action of the permanent magnet and the second part
28 that is the residual product left at the bottom of the vial. The separation was performed for both
29 samples, that from now on will be named A_m , B_m (magnetic part) and A_{nm} , B_{nm} (non-magnetic)
30 respectively.
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38 XPS spectroscopy analysis was performed on the two samples A (red lines) and B (black lines),
39 distinguishing between the magnetic and non-magnetic part. The extended spectral region (see
40 Figure S3 in the Supplementary Information) scans display the contribution coming from the
41 main elements involved in the reaction process for both the samples: carbon, iron, oxygen and
42 chloride. The Fe 2p peak was investigated in detail and the spectra are reported in **Figure 4.**
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Figure 4. XPS regional scan of iron showing the deconvolution of the Fe2p peak. (a) Sample A_m (red line) and A_{nm} (red dashed line) and sample B_m (black line) and B_{nm} (black dashed line). Spectral lines were normalized to the C1s signal. Panels (b) and (c) show the fitting analysis of the samples B_m and B_{nm} respectively, to check the different coordination state of Fe.

The iron intensity signal from the magnetic and non-magnetic parts of sample A (red lines) is very low and nearly identical, Figure 4(a). In addition, the binding energy comes from the stoichiometric Fe₂O₃ oxide rather than metallic Fe 2p. The spectra obtained from the magnetic part of sample B (B_m, black line) has a marked contribution coming from metallic Fe. Figures 4b and 4c show the results of the deconvolution of the Fe2p electron core-level of the samples B_m and B_{nm} respectively. The peak positions of Fe2p_{3/2} and 2p_{1/2} depend on the ionic state of Fe. In particular, we have considered, for the fit procedure, three different ionic states identified by: Fe⁰ (metallic state), Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ (oxide state) associated with the satellite peaks that are sensitive to the oxidation states. **Table 1** reports the concentration of the Fe coordination states

for the B_m and B_{nm} samples. Therefore, from the obtained results, if we assume that iron is mostly contained inside the CS samples, it oxidized during the reaction process.

Table 1. Concentration from fit analysis of the different Fe coordination.

Sample	Concentration from fit analysis		
	[%]		
	Fe^0	Fe^{2+}	Fe^{3+}
B_m	54	20	26
B_{nm}	-	-	100

The XRD patterns gave additional information on the samples as reported in the Figure S4 (in the Supplementary Information), in which the graphite structure presents a strong dependence with the sample type. In particular, the sample B_m shows a better graphitization (graphite with the conventional AB stacking) and the presence of an initial structuring of the diffraction pattern from the catalytic nanoparticles of small size associated to α -Fe, Fe_3C and graphite-2H phases. The hysteresis loops, acquired at room temperature, allowed probing the magnetic properties of the samples. **Figure 5** reports the magnetization curves of the two portions of samples A (Figure 5a) and B (Figure 5b). Red (black) curves refer to the magnetic (non-magnetic) part of the samples. Notice that the corresponding ordinate axes (magnetic moment per unit mass) have different scales for the magnetic (left scale) and non-magnetic (right scale) components of the specimen. In all the plots of the (diamagnetic) signal from the probe and from the sample holder is already subtracted.

Figure 5. Magnetization curves of (a) sample A and (b) sample B. Red (black) curves refer to the magnetic (non-magnetic) part of the samples. Notice that the corresponding ordinate axes (magnetic moment per unit mass) have different scales for the magnetic (left scale) and non-magnetic (right scale) components of the specimen. The negative asymptotic slope of the non-magnetic plots is due to the diamagnetic contribution of the carbon spheres, which becomes relevant when the ferromagnetic signal is very small.

Therefore, the negative asymptotic slope observed for the non-magnetic plots is due to the diamagnetic contribution of the carbon spheres, which becomes relevant when the ferromagnetic signal is very small. On the other hand, the incomplete saturation even at magnetic fields of 1T, detected for the magnetic samples, can be ascribed to the iron-based particle size distribution. In fact, larger size particles (or even more elongated ones) have sufficient magnetic anisotropy to possess a permanent and non-fluctuating magnetic moment, giving rise to hysteresis, whereas clusters with smaller size are in a superparamagnetic regime and contribute to the magnetization loop with a Langevin-like function.^[20]

Table 2 reports the main magnetic parameters extrapolated from the four hysteresis loops: the coercive field (column 2), the estimated saturation magnetic moment per unit mass (column 3), and the number of magnetic iron atoms per unit sample mass (column 4) calculated from

column 3, assuming that the magnetic moment for a Fe atom is 1.2 bohr magnetons, a value compatible for compounds such as maghemite (γ -Fe₂O₃), magnetite (Fe₃O₄), and cementite (Fe₃C). The last compound is clearly revealed in the x-ray diffraction analysis of sample B_m (see Figure S4 in the Supplementary Information) and already associated to a superparamagnetic response when in nanoparticle form.^[21,22] An accurate comparison with the XPS data, the amount of magnetic iron with respect to the overall Fe content, is about one order of magnitude less, for the magnetic parts of the two samples. Therefore, only a small fraction of the iron content exhibits an appreciable magnetic response. This is not surprising if we consider that even the residual powder not selected by the magnetic separation method (namely, samples B_{nm} and A_{nm}), contains comparable amount of iron with respect to their magnetic counterparts.

Table 2. Magnetic measurements results for the four CS samples.

sample	H _c	M _s	N _{Fe}
	[Oe]	[emu/g]	[atoms/g]
A _m	290	0.17	1.4×10 ¹⁹
A _{nm}	330	0.0018	1.5×10 ¹⁷
B _m	270	0.70	5.8×10 ¹⁹
B _{nm}	300	0.0053	4.4×10 ¹⁷

Observing more accurately the magnetic results, we note that the shapes of the hysteresis loops of samples A and B are very similar, although not identical. However, the magnetic response of sample B is much higher than that of sample A by a factor around four for the magnetic portions. This is in agreement with a greater iron content in sample B detected by XPS (by a factor of about six). The measured coercive field (H_c) for the samples is comparable to that reported in the literature for other Fe filled carbon species like multi-walled nanotubes.^[23,24]

1 From the results illustrated, a possible mechanism for the formation of CSs can be inferred. In
2 the reaction process, the iron has the role of catalyzing the synthesis of carbon spheres and
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4 activates the carbon atoms produced by the dissociation of acetylene C_2H_2 and the other carbon-
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6 containing species. In the hot zone, the iron atoms aggregate into nanoparticles that are later
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8 encapsulated during the formation of quasi-spherical carbon shells. With increasing reaction
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10 time, the Fe nanoparticles present in the carbon shells become smaller and can delocalize in the
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12 carbon sheets eventually leaving the spheres that have formed. Therefore, it is possible that Fe
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14 is not always present in the CSs or its concentration is below the detection limit. In addition,
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16 there is a dependence of the CSs final structure upon the gas flow rates, being all the other
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18 parameters left unchanged (reaction temperature, and time, ferrocene concentration, solvent,
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20 cooling down time). In particular, the Ar/ C_2H_2 changes the average relative speed of the Carbon
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22 atoms and Fe nanoparticles in the reaction zone. The acetylene gas is also a Carbon atom
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24 supplier. The Ar and C_2H_2 were both made available in larger quantities for the sample denoted
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26 as B compared to sample A. It appears that in sample A the final graphene sheets arrangement
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28 in the spheres is less ordered (see Figures 1 and 2) and less Fe content is also found compared
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30 to sample B. Therefore, for sample A, the gas flux is sufficient to form the spheres but these are
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32 less graphitic and most amorphous. In practice, the 250/50 sccm Ar/ C_2H_2 gas flux adopted for
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34 sample B are better for synthesizing and separating carbon spheres of better graphitic character
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36 while keeping into account that the more Fe catalyst is present in the structure.
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48 *2.2 Solar cells*

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50 In the last two decades, carbon nanomaterials (e.g. carbon nanotubes, fullerenes) with
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52 photogeneration properties have been exploited for solar energy conversion applications. [25]
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54 One possible configuration employs the heterojunctions formed between materials with suitable
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56 band gaps in order to cover a wider range of the solar spectrum response. In particular,
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58 nanomaterial/semiconductor solar cells made of crystalline semiconductors, such as Si, and
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1 carbon nanomaterials, rely on the cooperative action of Si, that photogenerates electron-hole
2 pairs and the nanomaterial (constituted of carbon) film that acts both as a photogenerator and
3
4 as charge-transporting layer. [26]
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7 Consequently, based on our experience, [26-27] we developed a device to study the photon-energy
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9 conversion ability of the CS films deposited on a Si substrate, as illustrated in Figure S4 in the
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11 Supporting Information. The devices obtained from the deposition of the magnetic portion of
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13 samples A and B show a photocurrent response, while from the non-magnetic part no significant
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15 results were found.
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19 In particular, **Figure 6** shows the electrical response of the CS/Si best device, obtained from
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21 the sample B_m, in the dark state and under illumination (light state), enlarged in Figure 6(b).
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23 The equivalent circuit diagram is the inset of Figure 6(a). From the analysis of the light state
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25 curve, the short-circuit current density $J_{sc} = 0.42 \pm 0.05$ mA/cm² and the open circuit voltage
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27 V_{oc} is about 0.21 ± 0.01 V. The PCE achieved is about 1.2 ± 0.2 %, with a fill factor $FF = 0.3$,
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31 Figure 6(c).
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34 The obtained results are markedly below what our group found for single as well as multi walled
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36 carbon nanotubes employed in similar devices. [26-27] Nevertheless, the investigated CS-Si
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38 heterostructures show a light energy conversion ability in all the spectral range explored with a
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41 higher response in the visible range, Figure 6 (c).
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Figure 6. Device characterization. (a) Electrical response of the best CS/Si device under dark (black line) and under illumination (red line). Inset: equivalent circuit diagram. (b) Enlargement of the response curves reported in (a). (c) External quantum efficiency (EQE).

The devices prepared with the magnetic samples gave a response and B_m is the best. This last finding is very interesting and although we are still investigating on this point, we can gather some preliminary statements. There are some differences in the two CS samples that we can briefly summarize as follows: 1) the average diameter is similar but the graphene layers inside the spheres are more disordered in sample A compared to sample B; 2) the spheres in sample B tend to be more aggregated than sample A; 3) the sample B_m has higher iron content than sample A_m , and the iron is present in metallic and oxidized state. These structural differences strongly influence the observed light response. The CS films constitute a disordered two-

1 dimensional network of variable conductivity. This variation originates from the presence of
2 high-conductivity clusters separated by small low-conductivity ones. The CSs in the clusters
3 are randomly arranged with several contacts and with local defects that act as electronic energy
4 barriers, limiting the conduction. Therefore, since the photoelectrons produced upon light
5 irradiation are weakly localized, percolate between the conducting regions by thermally induced
6 hopping, and tunnel through less-conducting regions. This description reasonably supports the
7 best response found for sample B (that showed the more ordered inner and outer structure
8 favoring the conduction), with respect to A, and for magnetic samples, with respect to
9 nonmagnetic ones. In addition, the observed CSs propensity to arrange in a necklace
10 configuration in touch with each other facilitates the electron flow and collection in the device.
11 The presence of iron inside the structure improves the photoresponse since it makes available
12 additional charges and helps the conduction process. This behavior has been already found and
13 described in detail for multi-walled carbon nanotubes. [28-31]
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34 *2.3 Electrochemical sensors*

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39 In the electrochemical field, the exploitation of nanomaterials has boosted the tailored and high
40 performant sensor and biosensor production thanks to physical, chemical, and catalytic
41 properties of nanoparticles.^[32-35] The advantage of decreasing scale in electrochemistry can be
42 ascribed to enhanced mass transport as well as reduced capacitive charging^[36], conferring to
43 to the nano-modified sensors and biosensors improved electroanalytical performances in terms
44 of electron transfer, sensitivity, working and storage stability, to name a few. Among the
45 carbonaceous materials, carbon nanotubes and graphene are the most employed in the
46 electrochemical sensors and biosensors development,^[37,38] while few papers report on CSs in
47 electrochemical devices.^[39-45] In addition, none of these papers investigated the CSs
48 electrochemical behaviour in terms of magnetic and non-magnetic properties. For this reason,
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1 we directly evaluated the electrochemical performance of the CSs by drop casting a dispersion
2 of CSs on electrochemical chips (E-chips) and analysing the response towards several clinically
3 relevant analytes. The E-chips were modified using magnetic and non-magnetic CSs, and tested
4 towards ascorbic acid, cysteine, NADH and dopamine analytes.
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9 In detail, we investigated the electrochemical behaviour of E-chips modified with the dispersion
10 of A_m , A_{nm} , B_m and B_{nm} , and we observed repeatable results only in the case of B_m and B_{nm} .
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12 Consequently, **Figure 7** only reports the cyclic voltammeteries of the analytes tested using E-
13 chip modified with B_{nm} (red line) and with B_m (green line). Furthermore, to better understand
14 the effect on the E-chip modification, cyclic voltammeteries using unmodified E-chip are
15 reported (dashed black line). In the case of reversible behaviour, as in the case of dopamine, we
16 observed a significant decrease of peak to peak separation using E-chip modified with the
17 dispersion B_m , demonstrating a better electron transfer. In addition, an increase of intensity of
18 anodic and cathodic peaks was observed, probably ascribed to the higher number of
19 electroactive sites. In the case of irreversible behaviour (i.e. ascorbic acid, cysteine and NADH)
20 we have observed a relevant decrease of potential for oxidative reaction, demonstrating the
21 electrocatalytic properties of the B_m material. Moreover, the cyclic voltammeteries achieved in
22 only phosphate buffer (working solution without the analyte) demonstrate low capacitive
23 current, confirming the good conductivity of B_m material. For understanding the reason of this
24 behavior, we correlated the structure with the electrochemical response. The low repeatability
25 of the A samples could be ascribed to the more disordered arrangement of the graphene layers
26 inside the spheres (see Figure 2) in respect to the B samples which also showed a better
27 repeatability (RSD% lower than 10%).
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51 Regarding the E-chip modified with B_m and B_{nm} , we suppose that the higher electrochemical
52 performances of that modified with B_m are ascribed to the iron content present in the magnetic
53 CSs, taking into account that some authors reported the importance of metal impurities in the
54 electrocatalysis of carbon nanotubes and graphene materials. For instance, Compton group,^[46]
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1 highlighted that metal impurities may cause the observed “electrocatalysis” using carbon-
2 nanotube-modified electrodes and Pumera group claimed that “metal-free” electrocatalysis of
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4 the oxygen reduction reaction is due to the metallic impurities present in graphene materials.
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7 ^[47] We can conclude that the presence of iron in CSsc can cover a double aspect is able: 1) to
8
9 confer the magnetic properties to the material as well as 2) to improve the electrochemical
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11 performances of the magnetic modified CSs E-chips.
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14 For instance, Banks et al., ^[46] highlighted that the electrocatalysis for carbon nanotube modified
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16 electrode is due to the metal impurities in the carbon nanotubes that most probably consist
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18 Fe₂O₃. Similar results have been obtained for graphene by Pumera et al. ^[47] that observed that
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20 an oxidative treatment of graphite samples is not sufficient to get rid of the impurities associated
21
22 to the chemically reduced graphene that alter the electrochemical properties significantly.
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26 To this regard, the iron present in the magnetic CSs improves the electrochemical performances
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28 of the modified E-Chip and, at the same time, confers to CSs magnetic properties which can be
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30 exploited to easily manage this carbon-based material.
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Figure 7. Cyclic voltammograms recorded in presence of 2 mM of (a) ascorbic acid, (b) cysteine, (c) dopamine, (d) NADH, (e) serotonin and (f) phosphate buffer. All the experiments were carried out in 0.05 M phosphate buffer containing 0.1 M potassium chloride (pH 7.4) at a

1 scan rate of 50 mV/s using bare E-chip (black dashed line) and E-chip modified with no
2 magnetic CSs (B_m , green line) or with magnetic CSs (B_{nm} , red line).
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7 **3. Conclusion**

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11 This paper describes a tailored vapor assisted chemical deposition method to obtain carbon
12 spheres of nanometric dimensions. The cost of the synthesis process is reasonable and the yield
13 is very high with a reduced presence of side products. Changing some of the growth parameter
14 during the synthesis allows obtaining spheres of different morphology and structure. Most
15 importantly, the iron catalyst employed in the reaction confers a marked magnetic response at
16 room temperature to portions of the synthesis products. Therefore, the samples shared into two
17 halves magnetic and non-magnetic are analyzed separately. The inner and outer structural
18 features of the spheres and the active contribution of iron mark the difference in the
19 photoresponse as well as in the electrochemical performance of the two samples. The results
20 are interesting and clearly show that the presence of residual iron inside the spheres is not
21 detrimental for some targeted applications. These promising outcomes deserve further
22 experimental investigation in order to optimize the CSs structural properties together with a
23 detailed theoretical description that is still lacking. The low intrinsic mass of the spheres
24 recommends their possible use as components in composite materials. The abundance of defects
25 makes them highly reactive, suggesting applications as catalyst support and the possibility of
26 further surface chemical modifications in a wide range of chemical or biological systems.
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51 **4. Experimental Section**

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54 *4.1 Preparation of carbon spheres*

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1 The carbon spheres were synthesized following a chemical vapor deposition process performed
2 in a horizontal furnace. The furnace was first heated up to the growth temperature under argon
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4 atmosphere at ambient inert pressure (760 Torr). Ferrocene ($\text{Fe}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$, 2.3% wt), used as a
5
6 catalyst, dissolved in dichlorobenzene at a concentration of 0.05 gml^{-1} . A glass syringe
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8 containing the solution injects drops of liquid at a constant rate (5 ml/h) with the help of argon
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10 and acetylene gases that act as carrier and additional carbon precursor respectively. The
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12 vaporized solution and the gas mixture enter into the chamber via a stainless pipe directly into
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14 a quartz tube placed in the hot region of the furnace kept at $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The synthesis products
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16 collected from the tube appear in the form of black powder and small agglomerates. Two
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18 samples that differ in gas flux used during the reaction process were analyzed in this paper. The
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20 first was grown with argon/acetylene flux (50 sccm and 25 sccm, respectively), named sample
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22 A and the second with argon/acetylene flux (250 sccm and 40 sccm, respectively), named
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24 sample B. No post-growth purification processes were applied to the obtained powders.
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31 32 33 34 *4.2 Sample Characterization* 35 36 37

38 The CS morphology and structure were examined using a field emission gun scanning electron
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40 microscopy (FEG-SEM, Leo Supra 35), equipped with energy dispersive X-ray (EDX), and a
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42 transmission electron microscopy (TEM, cold FEG Hitachi HF2000 operated at 200 kV
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44 voltage). For the TEM analysis, the synthesis products were dispersed in ethanol (95% solution)
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46 and sonicated for half an hour. The samples were then dropped onto a copper grid (mesh 300)
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48 covered with a thin holey carbon film and dried before investigation.
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51 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) data were acquired using an ultrahigh vacuum PHI
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53 1257 system equipped with a hemispherical analyzer, operating in the constant pass energy
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55 mode (with the total energy resolution of 0.8 eV) using a non-monochromatized Mg $K\alpha$
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57 radiation source. The distance between the sample and the anode was about 40 mm, the
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1 illumination area was about $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ and the analyzed area was $400 \times 400 \text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$ with a take-off
2 angle, between the sample surface and the photoelectron energy analyzer, of 45° . The energy
3 scale was calibrated with reference to the binding energy of the C1s at 284.8 eV with respect to
4 the Fermi level.
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9 The samples crystalline structure was investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Siemens
10 5000 diffractometer with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation in Bragg-Brentano geometry. JCPDS cards 65-4899,
11 35-0772 and 41-1487 were used to index α -Fe, Fe_3C and graphite- 2H, respectively.
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16 Electron energy loss spectra (EELS), taken ex situ at room temperature on the samples, were
17 recorded in the same PHI 1257 system equipped with an electron gun ($E_p = 300 \text{ eV}$, $\Delta E = 0.7$
18 eV). A room temperature micro-Raman spectra of the as-synthesized carbon spheres were
19 recorded with a LABRAM spectrometer (Horiba-Jobin Yvon, $\lambda = 633 \text{ nm}$, $1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ spatial
20 resolution, and $\sim 2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectral resolution) equipped with a confocal optical microscope ($100\times$
21 MPLAN objective with 0.9 numerical aperture and 0.15 mm work distance).
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Magnetic characterization was performed with an alternating gradient magnetometer (MicroMag 2900AGM, Princeton Measurements Corporation). Hysteresis loops were collected at room temperature with magnetic fields up to 1T for as synthesized CSs and for selected partitions of the spheres obtained by magnetic separation using a permanent magnet, as explained in section 2.1.

Photocurrent measurements were carried out at room temperature on CS films deposited on patterned silicon substrates (provided by Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK), Trento-Italy). CSs were dispersed in ethanol (30 mg/mL) and ultra-sonicated for one hour to improve the dispersion. Films of CS were fabricated following a vacuum filtration process of volume aliquots of the dispersion on cellulose filters (see Figure S3(a) in the Supplementary Information). The filters were cut and deposited by dry-transfer printing technique described in detail elsewhere ^[20] on the top of the device. The device consists of an n-doped crystalline silicon covered by thermal SiO_2 (300 nm). The SiO_2 has a patterned bare Si window (2×2

1 mm²) delimited by SiO₂ (the device active area is 0.04 cm²) with Au/Cr back and front contact
2 electrodes evaporated on SiO₂ (see Figure S3(b-c) in the Supplementary Information). The light
3 energy conversion ability of the films was tested using a solar simulator under AM 1.5 spectral
4 illumination (from LOT-Oriel, incident power 100 mWcm⁻²). The output power density was
5 calibrated using a power meter.
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10 11 12 13 14 *4.3 Electrochemical sensor*

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19 *4.3.1 Electrochemical chip fabrication:* Electrochemical chips (E-chip) were produced with a
20 245 DEK (Weymouth, UK) screen-printing machine. Graphite-based ink (Electrodag 423 SS)
21 from Acheson (Milan, Italy) was used to print both the working and auxiliary electrode.
22 Silver/silver chloride ink (Electrodag 477 SS) was used to print the pseudo-reference electrode.
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24 The substrate has been a flexible polyester film (Autostat HT5) purchased from Autotype Italia
25 (Milan, Italy). The diameter of the working electrode was 0.3 cm resulting in a geometric area
26 of 0.07 cm².
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39 *4.3.2 Preparation of CSs Dispersions:* The produced CS powders were dispersed in a
40 hydro/organic media. 10 mg of the selected powders were firstly dissolved in 5 mL of N,N-
41 dimethylformamide, and subsequently 5 mL of distilled water were added. The mixture was
42 sonicated for 1 h at 59 kHz. The dispersion was stored in the dark at room temperature.
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51 *4.3.3 Procedure for E-chip modification:* E-chip was modified by drop casting. 2 μL of the
52 dispersion onto the working electrode surface. The modified E-chips were interrogated after the
53 solvent of the dispersion completely evaporated.
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61 **Supporting Information**

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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29 Supporting Information 30

31 32 33 34 **Influence of Iron catalyst in the Carbon Spheres Synthesis for Energy and** 35 **Electrochemical Applications** 36 37 38

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42 *Manuela Scarselli**, *Francesca Limosani*, *Maurizio Passacantando*, *Franco D'Orazio*, *Michele*
43 *Nardone*, *Ilaria Cacciotti*, *Fabiana Arduini*, *Eric Gautron*, *Maurizio De Crescenzi*
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50 This file contains additional results obtained from other experimental characterizations that
51 helped understanding the inner structure and the composition of the two samples A and B.
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57 The EELS spectra obtained from samples A and B helped understanding carbon hybridization
58 in the material, **Figure S1**. In particular, the CS spectra show two typical features due to π and
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$\sigma + \pi$ plasmons similar to those obtained from the carbon sp^2 signal of highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG).^[1] However, both plasmons energies are shifted towards lower energy with respect to those of HOPG (located at 7 and 28 eV). This behavior evidences that the CS electronic properties are different from those of graphite mainly because of the nanometric dimension of the material, as already observed for multiwalled carbon nanotubes. No significant differences in the magnetic and non-magnetic parts of both samples appear in the EELS signal. For these samples, the presence of iron catalyst particles inside the structure does not affect the carbon bonds in the graphene planes arrangement.

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Figure S1. EELS spectra from the magnetic (a) and (b) and non-magnetic (c) and (d) portions of sample A and sample B, respectively.

The Raman spectroscopy gave information on carbon structural order. The analysis was restricted to the two main Raman shifts located around 1350 cm^{-1} and 1580 cm^{-1} , commonly denoted as D- and G-bands for carbon sp^2 vibrational modes, **Figure S2**. The D-band is associated with the vibrations of carbon atoms with dangling bonds for the in-plane terminations of disordered graphite, i.e. diagnostic of disorder in the carbon structure. [2]

Figure S2. Raman shifts D- and G-bands for carbon sp^2 vibrational modes from the magnetic (black line) and non-magnetic (red line) portions of: (a) sample A and (b) sample B. The calculated I_G/I_D ratio is also reported.

The G-band originates from the vibration of sp^2 - bonded carbon atoms in a two-dimensional hexagonal lattice, as in a graphite layer, thus giving a diagnostic of structural order. [2]

The intensity of the D and G bands is comparable for each magnetic part (A_m and B_m); this behavior highlights the high number of structural imperfections. These defects originate both from the disorder in the graphene sheets relative orientation in the sphere and from the presence of pentagon and heptagon carbon rings that are necessary to bend the graphene during the spheres formation. Nonetheless, both the D and G peaks are sharp, suggesting the presence of only C sp^2 hybridization form in the nanostructure. On the contrary, the G and D bands of the non-magnetic portions (A_{nm} and B_{nm}) not only decrease in intensity but also broaden thus indicating a higher degree of disorder and increase of the size distribution of the carbon

1 nanostructures in the samples. The evaluation of the ratio of the relative intensities of D- and
2 G-bands ranges between $I_D/I_G = 1-1.1$, a value comparable to those reported in the literature for
3 similar CSs. [3-5]
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10 **Figure S3** displays the XPS spectra obtained from the two samples A (red lines) and B (black
11 lines) over the extended spectral region. The scans display the contribution coming from the
12 main elements involved in the reaction process for both the samples: carbon, iron, oxygen and
13 chlorine.
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41 **Figure S3.** XPS wide energy scans from the four CS samples. (a) Samples A_m and A_{nm} (red
42 lines) and (b) samples B_m and B_{nm} (black line).
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49 **Figure S4** displays the XRD patterns of the different samples. In the left panel the peak of the
50 (002) peak of the hexagonal graphite structure is reported. We can observe that the (002) peak
51 presents a strong dependence with the sample type. In particular, the (002) peak exhibits an
52 asymmetric shape, and, for the sample B_m, there is a clear shift towards the right position of the
53 (002) peak, that is related to a better graphitization (graphite with the conventional AB stacking).
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The right panels of Figure S-2 report the 36 – 57° range patterns that prove the presence of catalytic nanoparticles. The corresponding intensity peaks associated to α -Fe, Fe₃C and graphite- 2H phases were indexed. The presence of an initial structuring of the B_m sample diffraction pattern is observed, suggesting the existence of small sized catalytic particles.

Figure S4. XRD patterns of samples A_m (red line), A_{nm} (red dashed line), B_m (black line) and B_{nm} (black dashed line). Left panel shows the C(002) peak attributed to the graphitic materials. In the right panels angle range where the trace of the catalytic particles is observed, the associated signals for α -Fe, Fe₃C and graphite- 2H are indexed. Notice that a downshift in the centre of gravity of the (002) can be appreciated, which could indicate the presence of other types of carbon material. JCPDS 65-4899, 35-0772 and 41-1487 were used to index α -Fe, Fe₃C and graphite- 2H respectively.

According to our experience with carbon nanotubes, ^[6] we developed a device to study the photon-energy conversion ability of the CS films deposited on a crystalline Si substrate. The

Figure S5 reports the steps of the device preparation: the filter obtained from the CS solution

(Figure S-5a), the sketch of the Si-based surface device (Figure S5b), and the SEM image (Figure S5c) of the dry transfer CSs deposition on the device active area.

Figure S5. Device fabrication for energy conversion measurements. (a) Filter for CSs deposition, sketch of the device (b) and (c) SEM micrograph of the active area after CSs deposition from filter (a).

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